

Between Farms and Forks: Food industry perspectives on the future of EU food labelling

Abstract

This study assesses how information about environmental goods provision can contribute to an integrative food labelling framework within the European Unions' Farm to Fork Strategy. By applying Q-methodology with 43 food industry experts from four European member states, we identify common viewpoints among processors, retailers and labelling organisations. There is large consensus among food industry actors across Germany, Poland, Spain, and Sweden for introducing new food labelling initiatives. Applying factor analysis and using the qualitative information from the 43 in-depth interviews, we derive three distinct prototypes on a future European food label: 1) a producer-driven Ecosystem Services label, 2) a consumer-oriented information label, and 3) a new EU sustainable food label. These label prototypes are partly country-specific and invoked by multiple stakeholder groups. We conclude that a future European Union food labelling framework must account for all three label prototypes. Policymakers are advised to embrace the diversity of viewpoints of food system actors, as these hold strong views on the driving factors of success and failure of labels.

Keywords

Ecosystem Services, Farm to Fork, supply chain, Common Agricultural Policy, food labels, Q methodology, value chain

JEL Codes

Q15, Q18, Q57

1. Introduction

Food production is a major driver of global environmental change, endangering global ecosystems, contributing to biodiversity loss, while using excessive amounts of fresh water, and interfering with nitrogen and phosphorus cycles (Fanzo et al., 2021; Poore & Nemecek, 2018; Willett et al., 2019). Current estimates suggest that food systems are responsible for approximately 37% of global greenhouse gas emissions (Crippa et al., 2021). To reduce the food system's environmental impact, a move towards more sustainable consumption patterns and significant improvements in food production are needed (Delabre et al., 2021; Halpern et al., 2022; Meyfroidt et al., 2022; Muller et al., 2017; Nguyen & Le, 2020; Willett et al., 2019). In the last decades, European policy-making is subject to a paradigm shift from a production-oriented to a multifunctional food system with a stronger emphasis on the environmental impacts (Bazzan et al., 2022). This paradigm shift sometimes manifests itself in stricter environmental regulation for receiving direct payments from the Common Agricultural Policy (Galli et al., 2022). European policymakers can choose from a range of policies to internalise the negative externalities of food production and promote environmental-friendly products (Just & Byrne, 2020; Galli et al., 2022). On the producer side, these challenges are addressed through various policy interventions, such as cross-compliance and subsidy payments defined in the Common Agricultural Policy of the European Union (Hasler et al., 2022; Pe'er et al., 2019). On the consumer side, taxes and product labels are popular to steer consumer behaviour towards more sustainable levels (Golan et al., 2001; Potter et al., 2021).

Product labels became popular as a policy instrument because they are relatively cheap to implement and maintain freedom of choice (Golan et al., 2001). Particularly for credence goods – products whose quality cannot be experienced by consumers – product labels become essential to highlight product characteristics and thus are important for consumers' purchasing decisions (Moussa & Touzani, 2008; McCluskey, 2000). Eco-labels give information about products' green credentials in order to provide information and alter consumer behaviour (Leach et al., 2016; Taufique, et al., 2019; Potter et al., 2021). These green credentials usually refer to ecological production standards or animal welfare measures, but do not specifically indicate producers' efforts to conserve biodiversity and other specific environmental goods (Nes & Ciaian, 2022).

The concept of ecosystem services could be a suitable framework for informing consumers about the environmental impacts of products (Jaung et al., 2016). Ecosystem services have emerged as an important tool to link the functioning of ecosystems to human welfare (Fisher et al., 2008). Defined as “the benefits humans derive from natural environments” (Constanza et al., 2007), ecosystem services are now widely recognised for systematically accounting natural capital (Schleyer et al., 2015). Exemplified by the EU biodiversity strategy, ecosystem services are increasingly recognised in political decision-making (Bouwma et al., 2018), and organisations such as the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) contribute to the mainstreaming and promotion of the concept (Albert et al., 2016).

The wide recognition of ecosystem services in European policy-making remains weak (Bouwma et al., 2018) and consumers are largely unaware of its use. Information campaigns or product labelling are one way to direct attention towards an improved communication of environmental benefits (Bougherara et al., 2020; Horne, 2009). To evaluate the potential of new labels, viewpoints from relevant stakeholder groups must be taken into account, as they will impact the entire food system (Galli et al., 2022). Stakeholders specialising in product-market placement and consumer behaviour can provide thorough evaluation of initiatives which appear promising (Castellari et al., 2018).

It is the objective of this paper to explore the viewpoints of food processors, label organisations, and retailers in four European countries on how to better communicate the services farmers and agriculture provide to humans. Put differently, we ask how information from different environmental goods can be accommodated in a new label. We apply Q-methodology to assess the viewpoints of food industry experts from Germany, Poland, Spain and Sweden to 1) map the diversity of individual stakeholder viewpoints, 2) define the prerequisites for a future label, and 3) identify country-specific characteristics for new product labels.

While many recent studies on food labels are quantitative and mainly deal with consumers (e.g., Edenbrandt & Lagerkvist, 2022; Altmann et al., 2022; Lin & Nayga Jr., 2022; Macready et al., 2020; Janssen & Hamm, 2014), the present study is qualitative-quantitative in nature. Investigating the diverse viewpoints of European food processors, retailers, and label organisations – the actors designing, implementing, and promoting labelling standards – can help addressing the most pressing issues of food labelling with respect to ecosystem services delivered along a product's value chain. Our analysis is based on 43 extensive in-depth interviews. Stakeholders were selected because of their individual expertise to critically assess whether the information on ecosystem services provision can be part of a new food label.

The remainder of the article proceeds as follows: Section 2 introduces food labelling in the context of the Farm to Fork (F2F) and Biodiversity Strategy. Section 3 discusses the role of different food

system actors and their inclusion in the study. Section 4 describes the methodology and data collection, and sections 5 and 6 report and discuss the results.

2. The EU food labelling policy context

2.1. Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy

To turn Europe into a climate-neutral continent by 2050, the EU has launched the Green Deal, with the F2F and the Biodiversity Strategy as its cornerstones (Purnhagen et al., 2021; Bazzan et al., 2022). The overarching goal of the F2F Strategy is to transition to a sustainable food system (European Commission, 2020a), whereas the Biodiversity Strategy has a primary aim to “put biodiversity on the path of recovery” (European Commission, 2020b). These broad political strategies consist of various proposed policy actions with the goal of contributing to lower greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity conservation, reduced pesticide use, and increased consumer empowerment (Schebesta & Candel, 2020).

The F2F Strategy foresees to make the food system more sustainable by imposing restrictions on fertiliser and pesticides and covering at least 25% of the EU’s agricultural land under organic farming by 2030 (European Commission, 2020a). Interlinked with the F2F Strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy aims to improve European biodiversity levels by increasing the amount of agricultural land under high-diversity landscape features to at least 10% (European Commission, 2020b). However, there are serious doubts about whether organic production and certification are sufficient to maintain and improve biodiversity and to reach climate targets as defined in the UN Sustainable Development Goals without substantial changes in consumption habits (Chiriaco et al., 2017). Therefore, holistic approaches that go beyond organic production and which also address the role of consumers in food labelling are recommended (Riccaboni et al., 2021). Until now, the F2F Strategy wants voluntary green credentials to be embedded in a sustainable food labelling framework and “[...] to empower consumers to make sustainable food choices” (European Commission, 2020a). While enormous progress has been made in quantifying product-specific environmental impacts (Clark et al., 2022; Leach et al., 2016), major challenges in how to communicate these impacts remain.

2.2. European food system actors

To enable a systemic change in the food system, all relevant actors and their activities within the system must be considered (Galli et al., 2020; Fanzo et al., 2021; Moschitz & Stolze, 2009). Producers and processors were identified as the first important stakeholder group. By producers, we refer to companies that turn raw farm produce into processed food, e.g., dairies or breweries. This group is familiar with current labelling procedures and well-informed about the relevant product markets and consumer behaviour. Moreover, by engaging in marketing measures, producers make use of labels to convey product credentials to consumers and to achieve market advantages (Castellari et al., 2018). A new food label would impact producers by affecting their sales, revenues, but also costs through additional certification.

The second group of food system actors comprises of third-party product labelling organisations. These organisations have the objective of evaluating the environmental footprints of products based on individually set criteria. They set, certify, monitor, and enforce quality standards, thereby contributing to a reduction of information asymmetries (Golan et al., 2001). People belonging to that group have extensive knowledge of certification processes and are familiar with the broad range of environmental standards and current debates around the extension of existing labels.

Labelling organisations typically increase the transparency of food production processes. From an economic perspective, this is particularly important for credence goods (McCluskey, 2000).

Thirdly, retailers of organic products are included as they are intermediaries between consumers and producers and thus have direct insights into consumer behaviour and the organisation of food value chains (Stolz et al. 2013). Retailers often have substantial market power (Stolz et al., 2013) and work with product labels and product placement, which makes them the “gatekeepers to crucial food system changes” (Boelsen-Robinson et al., 2021). Being an integral part of the food value chain, retailers have in-depth knowledge of the market structures of certified products, current environmental standards and trends in consumer purchasing behaviour. Retailers also play an important role in providing and mediating conflicting product sustainability information to consumers (Johnston & Szabo, 2011).

3. Method & data analysis

We applied Q-methodology with 43 individuals from the food processing industry in Europe to identify viewpoints regarding ecosystem services food labels. Q-methodology reveals social viewpoints underlying a stakeholder domain, given a concrete problem statement (Zabala et al., 2018). The method combines qualitative information from in-depth interviews with quantitative factor analysis to reveal attitudinal profiles of stakeholders, which provides statistical support to qualitative discourses (Brown, 1980; Watts & Stenner, 2005). A key advantage of this method is that it combines rigorous quantitative analysis with rich qualitative information in a supplementary and complementary fashion (Ellis et al., 2007; Sneegas et al., 2021), thereby allowing to identify similarities and differences among stakeholder discourses (Durning, 2006).

Participants are asked in individual interviews to sort predefined opinion statements into a grid, based on their personal level of agreement or disagreement with these statements (see Figure 1 for illustration below). The resulting sorting pattern, the so-called “Q-sort”, represents the individual subjective viewpoint regarding that research topic of the study. This sorting exercise is repeated with all involved stakeholders, leading to a multitude of differently sorted grids.

Figure 1: Applied Q-grid to accommodate the opinion statements

Q-sorts are then inter-correlated to detect commonalities among them, i.e., to detect joint patterns. This allows the dimension of the data to be reduced, as single Q-sorts are not interpreted as individual viewpoints, but as common sorting patterns which are interpreted in light of the adjunct interview data.

The pre-defined opinion statements constitute the central element of Q-methodology. Guided by the research question “How can information from different environmental goods be accommodated in a new label?”, a concourse of 92 statements was built. Current debates on implementing the EU Green Deal and particularly the F2F Strategy guided this process (see Figure A1 in the Appendix for an illustration of how statements are linked to F2F policy elements).

The initial collection of statements was informed by peer-reviewed literature, explorative expert interviews, and a workshop held with stakeholders in February 2020. As a result, statements were structured into the following categories: communication of labels, product value to consumers, the image of the enterprise, limits of labels, and ecosystem services.

After carefully revising the concourse, 47 statements were eliminated due to redundancy or overlapping with similar statements, leaving a total of 45 statements applied in the Q-interviews. This final set of 45 statements is the “Q-set” for this study. The statements are part of Table 2 in the results section.

To cover a broad geographical spectrum, we selected four countries, representing, the North, South, Centre, and East of the EU. Interviews were conducted from May 2020 to November 2020 in Germany, Poland, Spain and Sweden. We only considered producers who are already certified organic and thus have experience with certification and labelling. We prioritised third-party label organisations with high environmental standards and who constantly develop their labels. For the retailers, we aimed for a broad coverage, aiming for large players with big market shares.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we used an online tool for sorting the statements as part of the interviews (HtmlQ by Aproxima; see Sattler et al. (2022) for more discussion on this). During the interviews, participants were asked to think aloud to avoid misunderstanding and misinterpretation, as well as to create a space for personal experiences and subjectivity. The interviews were also recorded and later used to follow the sorting process as well as the thought processes of the participants. On average, an interview lasted about 75 minutes.

The procedure of the interviews was the same for all interviews and countries. We first asked interviewees to sort the statements into three major piles of agreement, disagreement, and neutrality. Next, the statements were sorted into the forced-choice distribution grid (see Figure 1). Finally, participants provided information about the statements they placed on the extremes of the grid (-5 “completely disagree” or +5 “completely agree”) as these statements were given the largest weight in the subsequent quantitative analysis.

The quantitative analysis was carried out with the “qmethod” package in R (Zabala, 2014 (accessed March 15th 2020)). 43 Q-sorts were inter-correlated using Pearson correlation. This provides a first indication of who sorted statements similarly. Principal Component Analysis was applied to reduce the dimensionality of the data and to identify commonalities among the interviewees. The factor loadings returned by the Principal Component Analysis indicate how strongly a Q-sort correlates with a specific factor. A Q-sort is often highly loaded on multiple factors and thus cannot be uniquely attributed to a specific factor. Therefore, varimax rotation was applied which maximises the share of explained variance and facilitates the ascription of Q-sorts to factors.

For determining the number of statistical factors extracted from the data, we applied statistical criteria suggested by the literature (Zabala et al., 2018), such as percentage of variance explained per factor (Cattell, 1966), the number of flagged Q-sorts per factor (Brown, 1980), the Kaiser-Guttman Criterion (Guttman, 1954), and Humphrey’s Rule (Fruchter, 1954).

4. Results

From the analysis of the 43 Q-sorts, five individual statistical factors emerged, fulfilling the previously mentioned statistical requirements. As shown in Table 1, all factors consist of at least two Q-sorts, have Eigenvalues larger than one and jointly explain more than 30% of the overall variance in the data. Using interview data and statement allocations, we interpreted and constructed viewpoints for each of the extracted factors.

Table 1: Statistical factor characteristics

	Number of Q-sorts	Eigenvalues	Explained Variance
F1	9	5.88	13.69
F2	9	4.98	11.59

F3	7	4.23	9.85
F4	5	3.21	7.46
F5	4	3.02	7.02

The statistical factors in the data showed large dispersion. Looking at the Q-set of 45 statements, there is no consensus found with respect to at least one statement, meaning that there is no single statement upon which the five factors mutually agree. Moreover, there are two statements out of the 45 to which all factors have a distinguished view. The first statement relates to whether or not ecosystem services provided through a producer must be related to the product (S37). The second statement addresses the issue of a graphical depiction of ecosystem services and discusses whether a traffic light system can serve as a suitable indicator for the environmental footprint of a product (S43). Table 2 highlights how each statement has been placed on the grid on average for each factor by emphasising the respective factor scores. That is, the statement allocation into the grid of a representative respondent, depicting the idealised Q-sort of that factor (e.g. for statement 1, respondents of factor 1 would allocate that statements into column 3, whereas respondents of factor 3 to column -1).

Table 2: Statements with factor scores

#	Statement	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	Certified labels can help to prevent greenwashing.	3	0	-1	0	2
2	The EU and individual countries should attest the credibility of labels.	-1	3	1	-2	1
3	Value chains are so complex that Ecosystem Services cannot be displayed using a label.	-4	-2	-3	-1	2
4	Ecosystem Services do not benefit from public recognition, unlike e.g. Fair Trade or animal welfare.	-2	3	1	-1	3
5	A label could help incentivise the production of Ecosystem Services in agriculture.	1	0	2	0	1
6	It would be useful to provide information on the ecological footprint of products with labels.	-1	2	2	-3	3

7	Information on Ecosystem Services is as important as the nutritional values of consumables.	2	-1	0	-1	-1
8	Consumers who buy organic products expect that these products provide the highest possible level of organic quality.	1	1	-1	-2	4
9	Investments in a company's image are more effective than investments in product trust.	-1	-3	-2	-3	2
10	QR-Codes are a suitable tool for providing consumers with the desired information.	1	-1	-1	0	-5
11	Complex products benefit more from a good company image than from Ecosystem Services certification on the products.	-2	-2	-2	0	1
12	Consumers can only understand a product's value chain by means of a label.	-2	-3	-3	-5	-4
13	The multiplicity of labels irritates consumers.	1	-1	1	5	5
14	Ecosystem Services provision is only viable when it entails economic benefits.	5	-4	-4	1	-3
15	The presentation of Ecosystem Services illustrates the producers' contribution to the common welfare.	0	0	-1	-1	-3
16	The communication of Ecosystem Services is an effective way to improve a company's image.	5	1	1	2	0
17	The communication of Ecosystem Services can show product differences to consumers.	3	1	0	1	1
18	Local communication are particularly appealing to consumers.	2	0	0	1	0
19	Transparent norms are essential in order to adequately represent Ecosystem Services.	4	5	4	2	2
20	Consumers would be willing to pay a product-related "fee" for the provision of Ecosystem Services.	1	0	0	-1	-4

21	Organic labels are more attractive than agri-environmental schemes.	-3	4	0	1	-1
22	The public discourse dictates which Ecosystem Services are perceived as important.	3	1	3	0	0
23	An additional environmental label could be used to realise market advantages.	0	2	4	-3	0
24	An increased willingness-to-pay for Ecosystem Services is not enough to cover the additional costs of implementing the services.	-3	0	0	4	-3
25	A limitation in the number of labels is necessary.	-3	-3	3	3	4
26	Different Ecosystem Services have varying potential to appeal to consumers.	2	3	2	0	0
27	Consumers are not willing to pay more for Ecosystem Services.	-5	-3	0	0	0
28	There is already too much labelled product information.	-2	-4	-3	3	4
29	Rather than quantifying the Ecosystem Services of entire products, companies should focus on evaluating individual inputs of their products.	-4	-2	-2	-4	-1
30	Ecosystem Services should relate to the whole product and not to individual components.	0	1	1	1	1
31	Rather than quantifying the Ecosystem Services of individual products, companies should focus on investments that benefit the perception of Ecosystem Services in general.	-3	1	-5	-2	-2
32	Additional information on the environmental consequences of production processes is useful for consumers.	1	5	3	-2	-2
33	The labelling of Ecosystem Services has to have a certain consumer awareness level to be successfully implemented.	-1	4	3	4	1

34	The norms of existing labels should be extended rather than new labels being created.	0	0	-3	3	-1
35	Ecosystem Services do not necessarily have to be linked to a product. The service itself counts.	-1	2	-5	3	-5
36	Information regarding Ecosystem Services is too complex to be reduced to a label.	-4	-1	-1	2	3
37	Ecosystem Services should have a clear reference to products.	0	-1	5	-4	3
38	Local Ecosystem Services especially have the potential to connect with the average consumer.	4	2	5	-1	-2
39	Consumers would be unable to cope with information on Ecosystem Services.	-1	-4	-2	1	0
40	Information provided by labels on organic products is not consistent. But consumers cannot tell the difference.	4	-1	-1	-3	5
41	Labels should target more than only one consumer group.	2	3	1	4	-3
42	Ecosystem Services labels can only target specific groups.	-5	-5	-4	-5	-2
43	A traffic light system for environmental friendliness would be a suitable tool to draw attention to Ecosystem Services.	0	-5	4	2	-4
44	Labels are important to create consumer trust.	3	4	2	5	-1
45	Product advantages can only be realised through emphasising individual benefits of Ecosystem Services for consumers (e.g. beautiful landscapes for recreation).	0	-2	-4	-4	-1

For the qualitative interpretation, and thus deriving precise viewpoints from the statistical factors, the statements that received the strongest positive and negative weighting from the individual factors were analysed first. Since these statements are decisive for the classification into factors, we looked at how the factors differed with regard to these statements. In the next step, we investigated individual comments on the opinion statements and examined similarities and differences between the factors with the help of the calculated z-scores. Similar to the factor scores, z-scores reflect how an opinion statement was rated on average by a factor. The difference

is that z-scores are the weighted average of the values to a statement, and are thus continuous. The factor scores in turn are integer values based on z-scores used to reconstruct the Q-sort of a factor (Zabala & Pascual, 2016). From the differences in the z-scores between the individual factors, we then determined which statements were allocated similarly into the grid and hence evaluated alike between the factors (indicating consensus with respect to opinion statements) and which were not (suggesting distinguishing viewpoints with respect to an opinion statement).

Viewpoint 1 – the transparent compensators

The viewpoint of the transparent compensators includes study participants from the 'Producer' and 'Labeller' domains, originating from Germany, Spain and Sweden. This factor expresses the viewpoint of nine participants in total, accounting for 13.7% of the study variance.

The transparent compensators have a distinctly positive opinion towards labels and see a large potential for a new label indicating ecosystem services provided along the value chain. Holders of that viewpoint indicated that current initiatives such as Food Watch¹ might enable label-based approaches. Consumers have trouble telling different labels apart and need transparency (S19, S20). This is not to say that consumers wouldn't pay for ecosystem services. This viewpoint argues that the public is willing to reward ecosystem services provision, provided that the labelling is genuinely credible (S27). Farmers on the other end have little intrinsic motivation to provide ecosystem services and require monetary compensation (S14).

Viewpoint 2 – the information seekers

The information seekers include study participants from all stakeholder domains, originating from Germany, Spain and Poland. As with the transparent compensators, there are nine participants representative of this perspective, accounting for 11.6% of the study variance.

Similarly to the transparent compensators, participants within this viewpoint see potential in new labels and emphasise the importance of trust-building for a successful label (S19). Moreover, the information seekers are distinguished from the transparent compensators by addressing the intrinsic motivations of farmers to provide ecosystem services. This viewpoint considers that labels have an important role in simplifying complex information for consumers. However, a traffic light system is perceived as too simplistic, potentially leading to adverse effects by misinforming consumers (S43). On the contrary, this viewpoint argues that consumers are keen to acquire product knowledge and thus appreciate additional information that helps in their decision-making process (S28, S32, S39).

Viewpoint 3 – the local pragmatists

The local pragmatists represent all stakeholder groups, with seven participants from Spain, Poland and Sweden. Their Q-sorts account for 9.8% of the study variance.

The main distinguishing element here is the emphasis on local farmers' markets as niches to sell products (S38). Similarly to the information seekers, financial compensation is considered to be of secondary importance and farmers are expected to deliver ecosystem services even without direct economic benefits (S 14). Participants highlighted that there are indirect benefits accruing from

¹ <https://www.foodwatch.org/en/foodwatch-international/>

labels, such as higher revenues due to higher demand. Many benefits from labels might come later (S 23).

In contrast to the information seekers, these participants clearly see the need for integrating ecosystem services into the value chain and thus think that ecosystem services must be linked to the products providing them (S 35). Also clearly contrasting to the second viewpoint is the perceived potential of using a traffic light system. The local pragmatists clearly opt for strict simplifications to reach a broad audience (S 43).

Viewpoint 4 – the cost concerned

As with the information seekers and the local pragmatists, the cost concerned consist of participants from all stakeholder domains. However, these originate from Spain and Poland only. The five participants account for 7.5% of the study variance.

This viewpoint is characterised by a more sceptical tone than the previous ones. Even though the cost concerned state that labels are important for trust-building (S 44), the sheer number of labels is considered to be confusing for consumers in their decision-making and buying behaviour (S 13). The participants are critical with respect to a traffic light system because in their view, it only works if the different levels are well defined and set ambitions to improve environmental footprints of production. From the producer's point of view, the colours must on the one hand create incentives to produce more sustainably, but on the other hand they must actually be realistically feasible. Their strongest point of criticism was related to the potentially cost-intensive restructuring of product lines based on new label requirements. Frequently, it is minor changes that are particularly costly and hence may lead to products no compliance with newly established labelling requirements.

This viewpoint further argues that it is the ecosystem services that count and not the sustainable value chain as such (S37). Hence, the key issue for a producer is to be involved in making nature conservation products, even if these are not related to their production cycles or highlighted with labels. This means that producers should be given the opportunity to provide ES, irrespective of whether the ES provision is directly linked to the products values chain. Instead, other marketing campaigns may help sustainable rebranding.

Viewpoint 5 – the overall sceptics

The last viewpoint – the overall sceptics – included participants from Germany, Poland and Sweden and encompassed all stakeholder domains. The Q-sorts for this factor account for 7% of the study variance.

Similarly to the cost concerned, participants who loaded onto this viewpoint are rather sceptical towards a new ES label. In contrast to financial problems, as pointed out by the cost concerned, the overall sceptics see a lack of knowledge among consumers as the main reason for failure (S 40, S 13). Instead of creating more labels, this viewpoint argues in favour of limiting the total number of labels available (S25).

Whereas the information seekers strongly believe that consumers desire to acquire more information about the environmental footprints of products, the overall sceptics disagree completely with this and also does not believe that digital tools, such as QR codes, will help to inform consumers (S 10).

5. Discussion

The aim of the paper was to 1) map the diversity of viewpoints of the individual stakeholders, 2) define the prerequisites for a future label, and 3) identify country-specific characteristics for new product labels.

The current study found five distinct viewpoints on the required institutional conditions for a new ecosystem services label in the European food processing industry, which in parts could support the introduction of a sustainable food labelling framework. Neither of these viewpoints is purely country or stakeholder-group specific. The attitudinal profiles found in the study span across countries and stakeholder domains. In general, it can be said that the first three viewpoints have a positive attitude towards a new label. By contrast, the fourth viewpoint represents a critical stance, and the fifth rejects a new label.

A closer look at the first three viewpoints allows to derive three possible label prototypes as a foundation for a sustainable labelling framework. However, each prototype stresses individual elements that might hinder the implementation of such a potential label, which must be addressed by policies accordingly.

5.1. Label prototypes

Revisiting the qualitative information from the interviews and the descriptions of the transparent compensators, the information seekers and the local pragmatists, we asked ourselves “What would a label look like if it were designed according to the ideas of the three positive viewpoints?” Therefore we derived three hypothetical label prototypes, each corresponding to either of the positively minded viewpoints.

1. *Ecosystem services producer label (corresponding to “the transparent compensators”)*

The first prospective label prototype is independent of previous product labels in that it constitutes a newly established label and is not an extension of an already existing label initiative. This label specifically focuses only on ecosystem services in the product values chain and no other product characteristics. Hence, the communication of this label to the public should particularly focus on these services to distinguish itself from restriction imposed by the EU organic label. The primary function of this label is to **signal** the provision of additional environmental public goods.

However, the incentives to participate in this labelling scheme would be similar to organic labelling scheme: farmers receive subsidies under pillar 2 payments and might realise market advantages due to their distinguished products. Moreover, this label is clearly characterised by rewarding locally producing farmers for the ecosystem services they provide and guaranteeing that a share of the product prices will be paid directly to them for the environmental public goods they provide. This follows the notion that farmers should be rewarded directly and remunerated according to their contribution of environmental public goods.

To ensure the credibility of this label, third-party organisations will be in charge of independently verifying the fulfilment of the required norms and standards. This principle corresponds to farmer associations, such as “Naturland”, “Bioland” or “Demeter” in Germany, which identify associations of organic farmers, processors and other agricultural producers for the purpose of promoting the joint marketing and control of the association's goods.

2. *Consumer information label (corresponding to “the information seekers”)*

As with the ecosystem services producer label, the consumer information label represents a newly established label initiative. However, its primary function is to mandatory **grade** products based on their environmental footprint.

The consumer information label follows the notion that consumers are capable to cope with additional information and that simplifications, such as 'traffic light' mechanisms are too simplistic and eliminate relevant aspects of additional services. Therefore, the label goes hand in hand with marketing campaigns to inform consumers about the content of the labelling prior to implementation in the field.

By contrast to the ecosystem services producer label, the consumer information label would not include governmental support or a guaranteed payment to the farmers. Instead, it is argued that the visibility of ecosystem services through the label will generate larger demand and create market advantages for accordingly labelled products. Hence, there is no need for a price intervention by guaranteeing higher product prices to farmers. Whereas the ecosystem services producer label had more of a signalling effect of voluntary environmental commitment, the consumer information label focuses on mandatory sustainability grading of product value chains.

Lastly, this label takes into account that different ecosystem services appeal differently to consumers. Hence, the focus and final design of the label will be determined by the ES provided by the producer. Depending on whether biodiversity, carbon storage or water-related ES are considered predominant by a farm's management, their products will be labelled accordingly.

3. *EU sustainable food label (corresponding to "the local pragmatists")*

The third label prototype follows a similar economic argument as the consumer information label, as it postulates that market advantages through increased demand can be realised with a new product label. The focus of this label is to establish credence through **signalling** sustainable credentials.

However, in contrast to the previous two prototypes, this label is not an entirely newly established one, but rather an extension of existing labelling schemes, such as the EU organic label, or part of planned policy frameworks, as the sustainable food labelling framework by the EU. Again, similarly to the consumer information label, the EU and member states are in charge of verifying the norms and standards of this label. In that line, farmers might receive governmental subsidies and realise market advantages when complying with EU organic farming and the new ecosystem services label initiative at the same time.

As with the consumer information label, the ecosystem services delivered are clearly linked to the product and described accordingly. That said, it is not sufficient to state that a product is good for the environment, but rather this information must be put in context by emphasising at which particular stage in production the ecosystem services-friendly practices are applied. Consequently, a supporting framework condition for EU sustainable food label is to simplify information about the environmental public goods along the value chain accordingly.

5.2. Commonalities among label prototypes

Although five distinctly different viewpoints emerged from the quantitative analysis, there are some points that were always similarly addressed in the qualitative interviews. Especially for the first three viewpoints from which the above label prototypes were derived, a few recurring themes stand out.

Establishing credence through transparent standards

Transparent standards constitute a key element of prospect sustainable labelling schemes, as a products' sustainability credentials cannot be verified by consumers. This information asymmetry has to be diminished by the rigorous implementation of transparent standards, backed up by credible institutions (Macready et al., 2020; Golan et al., 2001). Product brands play an enormous role in the credibility of environmental standards (Lassoued & Hobbs, 2005). For this reason in particular, it is important to ensure that established food brands are included in the new product label initiative in the form of certified pioneers. In the interviews, it was emphasised that many label initiatives only serve the purpose of greenwashing in order to create market advantages. It is necessary that strong institutions stand behind the new label and that transparent criteria are applied for awarding it.

In line with the opinion of the food industry experts who took part in our study, these institutions should either be represented by bottom-up associations, such as organic farming associations like Naturland or Demeter in Germany, or governmental bodies. Currently, there are a large number of product labels that are represented by non-farmers' associations whose standards are communicated without sufficient transparency (Porral & Levy-Mangin, 2016). As a result, trust in product labels, in general, is reduced and consumers are frequently left confused.

An additional argument for the involvement of strong institutions is the cost of certification. This is often argued as a major barrier for producers (Jaung et al., 2019), and was also addressed by our expert participants. They advised linking ecosystem services certification to the existing EU policy, similarly to what is already being done with organic farming under the second pillar of the EU Common Agricultural Policy.

Effectively channelling information to consumers

Our analysis showed that food industry experts have differing views on how to channel information to consumers. The present results are consistent with previous studies which have demonstrated that the cognitive burden at the time of purchase is enormous (Watson & Spence, 2007; Dijksterhuis et al., 2005; Grunert & Wills, 2007). Moreover, our experts highlighted that consumers react differently to the stimuli they are exposed to. Therefore, it is advisable not to rely on a single advertising mechanism, but to embrace the heterogeneity of consumer behaviour and rely on diverse tools. As environmental public goods are at stake in this context, the experts also emphasised the responsibility of the state to provide education campaigns for a new ecosystem services label. This argument is supported by Horne (2009), who argues that to be effective, labels must be embedded in some form of sustainable consumption strategy as the useful product information they provide is very limited.

Considering the communication towards the consumers, information technologies offer promising tools to help consumers to process complex information. Moreover, digital tools are argued to reduce information asymmetries and thus also diminish subsequent transaction costs of promising policies (Ehlers et al., 2021). QR codes are one of many available options mentioned in the interviews. However, this particular tool was not considered very promising and other avenues should be explored as well.

Highlighting the link of ES to the product

To prevent greenwashing, a clear link should be made between the product and its environmental performance. This ensures that consumers have the feeling that they are making a contribution to

environmental protection with their purchase decision. The ecosystem services concept for example is very extensive and can therefore be implemented on a wide variety of products. Throughout the derived label prototypes, the experts highlighted that the ecosystem services concept must be directly relatable to a product to be effective and influence purchasing decisions. That is to say, instead of investing in offsetting activities, companies must focus on implementing ecosystem services-friendly practices in their value chains. It is therefore not sufficient to engage in sustainable measures alongside production in order to improve the individual company image. Instead, these measures must be an integral part of the production process and indicate products direct environmental footprint (Leach et al., 2016).

Farmers' economic incentives

All the label prototypes agreed that economic incentives will play an important role in implementing the labels successfully. However, opinions differed on the precise design of payment mechanisms. The second and third label prototype agreed that the increased demand effects of the new labels are sufficient to reward farmers appropriately. The ecosystem services producer label, on the other hand, clearly emphasised that larger demand does not necessarily guarantee that more money ends up with the farmers. Therefore, they stress that governmental subsidies and an additional share of the product price must also go to farmers. This additional share should then precisely reflect the additional ecosystem services contribution.

There is substantial evidence for consumer demand for certified organic products and that consumers have a corresponding willingness to pay for appropriately labelled products (Janssen & Hamm, 2012; Janssen & Hamm, 2014). Following this principle, the experts introduced the argument that similar demand effects would also arise for a new label. However, research evidence also suggests that consumers are more willing to pay if it is ensured that additional payments are made to farmers (Emberger-Klein et al., 2016; Zander et al., 2013; Höhler & Schreiner, 2019). Consumers should be informed how farmers are rewarded for their additional effort. Ultimately, the new label alternative should be geared towards creating market advantages for farmers and thus providing incentives for sustainable management.

5.3. Policy implications: Link to F2F and Biodiversity Strategy

The F2F Strategy shapes an inspiring starting point for a sustainable and coherent food system across Europe. However, food system change in Europe entails numerous challenges. To achieve the objectives of the strategy, interconnected policies should be promoted in close coherence with Biodiversity Strategy. As stressed by Schebesta and Candel (2020), one remaining challenge for the success of the F2F Strategy is the unresolved ambiguity of defining “food sustainability”. This is of particular importance when conveying ecological background information on products. The concept of ecosystem services could address precisely this criticism and act as a transmitter to deliver metrics for environmental product footprints. On the basis of our expert group's familiarity with the ecosystem services concept (Matzdorf & Meyer, 2014) and current efforts to operationalise ecosystem services in national capital accounting (Hein et al., 2020; Keith et al., 2017; Daily & Matson, 2008), we see great potential for also using the concept for product labelling.

Schebesta and Candel (2020) have highlighted that “without the involvement and commitment of European food producers, processors, retailers and consumers, the F2F Strategy is unlikely to bring about much-needed change”. While much of agricultural policy currently focuses on the supply side and sustainable production, there is a particular need to stimulate the demand side and thus include processing and retail (Moschitz et al., 2021). Given the complex nature of the food system, it is clear that collaboration of different sectors and stakeholders involved is needed

for structural changes in the food system. The distinct prototypes found in our study are supported by multiple actor domains of the European food system and thus may lead the way towards integrative food policy and guide towards foundations of a sustainable labelling framework.

For a more concrete elaboration and design of the framework, we advise the continued involvement of various food system actors, as they can contribute significantly to the success of a new label through their experience and role in the system. Given that not all countries were always represented in the individual viewpoints, this should be taken into account in the concrete design of the labelling framework. Although all groups of actors are present in each viewpoint, they are not always from all the countries considered in the study. For example, there are no representatives from Poland in the ecosystem services producer label, no Swedish food system actors in consumer information label and no German stakeholders in the EU sustainable food label. This suggests that flexibility in implementation should be taken account of in the final design. This could affect products to be labelled or designated ecosystem services, as well as information provided on the label.

Reflecting on the revealed views of stakeholders within our research, it is evident that linking different approaches and policies of the agri-food system will be crucial to achieve systemic change. For a label approach, this could be, for example, a stronger linkage with the instruments of EU Common Agricultural Policy but also the consideration of approaches such as Natural Capital Accounting (Vysna et al. 2021). The policies should not only be coherent (Nilsson & Weitz, 2019) but synergetic.

5.4. Future research

This research has focused primarily on actors from the food industry and explored their viewpoints for the foundation of a new sustainable labelling framework. Further research should focus on farmers, as well as consumers, and their acceptance of new product labels resulting from the F2F strategy. Based on the label prototypes derived here, subsequent quantitative studies could be conducted with a focus on determining willingness-to-pay measures for appropriately labelled products. Using approaches from experimental economics, future research should investigate how consumers trade off attributes of labelled products in purchase situations and thus evaluate whether there is a market for ecosystem services labels.

6. Conclusion

The present study was designed to determine expert viewpoints regarding the potential of introducing an ecosystem services label on commodity products in Europe. Using Q-methodology, we quantified the subjective viewpoints of stakeholders from the food industry.

These viewpoints turn out to be heterogeneous, but not country-specific. Therefore, the introduction of a single comprehensive label is not advisable. Instead, strong individual initiatives and bundling of efforts by those actors who agree on the label design are more important. However, there are also opportunities for European initiatives, which may not always include all relevant actors, but which can act on a European level in the medium term.

Appendix

Figure A1: Alignment of selected statements (numbered circles) to objectives of the Farm to Fork Strategy and respective stakeholders

Figure A2: Graphical presentation of z-scores

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